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**School curriculum in Burkina Faso and Japan: A
literature review**

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Abstract

The education system in Burkina Faso has been reformed many times, but the latest system performance evaluations showed that those reforms did not yield the expected results. These reforms purported to provide appropriate training which content and methods align with the economic, technological, social, and cultural development, and value systems in Burkina Faso, Africa, and the world. Years later, the evaluation of the reform shows that education and vocational training decreased in quality and performance and they hardly adapt to the needs of the country. Informal economy employs many people, and research and innovation are still lagging and hardly contribute to people's well-being. Therefore, this research paper aims at exploring ways to go about educational policies and curriculum reforms which consider the cultural components, available technologies to meet the needs of the country in comparison to the Japanese educational system. It strives to find what Burkina Faso can learn from the educational system of Japan to meet the demands of the community, reach the goal of educational policies. This research did a literature review of the educational system, policies, and curriculum practices of Burkina Faso and Japan and found that Burkina Faso can learn from the way Japan develop the national curriculum, how its culture remains rooted in its school curriculum, and the progressive move to internationalize their educational system. Therefore, Burkina Faso can adapt and integrate its curriculum for the benefits of the learners and the community to boost socioeconomic development.

Key words: Burkina Faso, Community, Curriculum, Educational system, Japan

DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to my family which had to endure my absence during my stay in Japan for this research.

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List of accronyms and abbreviations

- BEP: Brevet d'Etudes Professionnelles
- BEPC : Brevet d'Etudes du Premier Cycle
- CAI: Computer-Assisted-Instruction
- CAL: Computer-Assisted-Learning
- CAP Certificat d'Aptitude Professionnelle
- CEAP: Certificat Élémentaire d'Aptitude Pédagogique
- CBNEF: Centre d'Education de Base Non-Formelle
- CRICED: Center for Research on International Cooperation on Educational Development
- EFA: Education for All
- ELT: English Learning and Teaching
- ICT: Information and Communication Technology
- JICA: Japan International Cooperation Agency
- NCS: National Course of Study
- MEXT: Ministry of Education, Culture, Sport, Science and Technology
- MOE: Ministry of Education
- NCEE: National Center on Education and the Economy
- OECD: Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development
- PDDEB : Plan Décennal de Développement de l'Education de Base
- PDSEB : Plan Décennal Education de Base
- PISA: Program for International Students Assessment
- SCADD : Stratégie de Croissance Accélération et de Développement Durable
- SBCE: School-based Curriculum Development
- SDGs: Sustainable Development Goals
- USAID: United States Aid for International Development
- TALIS: Teaching and Learning International Study

Equivalences of school levels/stages

- | | | |
|--------------------------|---|--|
| ➤ Primary school | ⇔ | Elementary school |
| ➤ Lower secondary school | ⇔ | Middle school ^{US} Junior secondary school ^{Britain} |
| ➤ Upper Secondary School | ⇔ | Upper school ^{US} Senior secondary school ^{Britain} |

INTRODUCTION

Education is a priority in Burkina Faso and the different governments of Burkina Faso took measures to reach quality education for all. However, evaluations conducted in 2016 show that the gap between what was expected and what is being done is still huge. In fact, many reforms and measures have been taken in this regard. The 2007 educational orientation law in its 14th chapter stated that the aim of education is to "provide appropriate training in its content and methods to the requirements of economic, technological, social and cultural development that takes into account aspirations and value systems in Burkina Faso, Africa, and the world". This aim was reiterated in the 2008 Decree on education policy. This policy aims at aligning curriculum and the labor market, introducing the notion of diversity, Information and Communication Technology (ICT), cultural awareness, community education, and harmonizing the different stages of our educational system.

One can agree that offering the appropriate education approach for the community will allow the government of Burkina Faso to reach the goal of quality education and the alignment between education and employment.

To address these issues, the National Economic and Social Development Plan aimed at reorienting research towards development objectives, promoting regional and international co-operation in the field of scientific and technological research, and reducing the under-employment of the rural workforce. Therefore, it should be clear how the content of our school curriculum is decided and how this curriculum can integrate and be adapted to the value system and the needs of the local populations. This will also help Burkina Faso reach the United Nations Fourth Sustainable Development Goal which is "achieving inclusive and equitable quality education for all." This study aims at exploring the curriculum content and practices of Burkina Faso and Japan to find ways to integrate socio-cultural realities of the students, the needs of their communities, and the labor market.

Research evolves following the dynamics of society. Therefore, new findings and theories also change our views of the world and new policies, strategies and techniques are adopted. This shows that the world is fast changing and we need to be innovative and proactive to keep pace. Bowser (2008) indicates that "As the amount and variety of technologies available to schools continues to grow, the potential for new and innovative ways to enhance students' educational experiences increases as well." Keeping pace with the changing world, one should make the wisest possible use of their resources and knowledge. As a developing country, the educational system of Burkina Faso is also at a developing stage. Inherited from the colonial period, the core content and the educational system of Burkina Faso is slow to change radically to embrace the new realities and challenges. Therefore, it is important for

educators and researchers to explore new horizons to learn and adapt our education system to the needs of our society. It can be done by finding ways on their own or by learning from countries where the educational systems tend to yield the expected outcomes that boost the development of these countries. To avoid many unsuccessful tryouts, learning from others and adapting to our realities can be a viable option to help cure the scourges that impede the development of Burkina Faso through quality education. This is the main reason why this study titled "*School curriculum in Burkina Faso and Japan: A literature review*" purports to explore the Japanese educational system and compare it with that of Burkina Faso to find ways to adapt or integrate socioeconomic realities in its curriculum contents and/or practices to get a simultaneous infusion of instruction and the skills needed to boost the development of the country through a strong educational system and a curriculum that align with the labor market. This may help to form new citizens with skills needed by the 21st century and their local communities. It can consist in including socio-economic and cultural realities in the school curriculum to respond to learners' needs and habits and reach the expectations that the communities placed upon the educational system. This research may help the Ministry of Education engage in a process of specific teacher-training activities, curriculum, and material design to make the Fourth Sustainable Development a reality for all the children of Burkina Faso. Teaching strategies should follow the guidelines of the strategic plan provided by the state through well-studied curricula and materials. Among others, that is a sustainable way to fight against unemployment, under-employment, and make the school curriculum relevant to the local populations.

This research aims at exploring the educational systems and the curriculum of Burkina Faso and Japan to find ways to adapt or design a sustainable school curriculum for Burkina Faso. There is an urgent need to design a curriculum which keep pace with the changing world while taking history and needs into account to train students to answer the development needs of the community. Likewise, Offorma (2016) says that a well-planned curriculum must reflect the culture of the people for which it is planned for it to be a functional curriculum. Every curriculum is based and covers the cultural universal, cultural specialties and cultural alternatives.

The essence of education is to produce the total man; someone who can use what he/she has learnt in school to solve problems. Culture is maintained and modified through education and so must be integrated in curriculum planning.

In this regard, curriculum planners should endeavor to integrate emerging cultures in the curriculum as society is dynamic. There are features of the society that should be included in the curriculum to make the learners functional members of the society.

The main objective of this study is to explore ways to integrate socio-cultural components in the school curriculum of Burkina Faso. It can be a strategy to train students in a way that corresponds to the needs of the country for its development. This strategy will allow community and students to take ownership of the educational system. Japan has gotten one of the best educations in the world and the best performer in OECD (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development) countries. This comparative study strives to take lesson from Japan by (1) finding out the gap between the educational policies and the skills needed, (2) understanding the connectedness between educational policies and socio-economic and cultural development and (3) learning how the implementation the school curriculum to respond to the needs for socioeconomic development.

To reach the objective, this paper is divided into four different chapters. Chapter I discusses the educational system of Burkina Faso and Japan through a historical overview. It also provides information on teachers' and students' profiles in the two countries.

Chapter II deals with the theories behind educational policies. It defines curriculum, discusses curriculum theory and practice.

Chapter III is about the educational policies and the national curriculum that education boards and personal should implement. It reviews the policies and the curriculum in the classroom.

Chapter IV suggests the lessons that Burkina Faso can learn from the Japanese educational policies, curriculum development and implementation regarding the objectives of this comparative study.

CHAPTER I. OVERVIEW OF THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEMS OF BURKINA FASO AND JAPAN

Educational system might have the same objectives in many countries, but their organization and administration change from one country to another. This chapter deals with the educational system of Burkina Faso and Japan to have more insight into their history. It deals with the history of the educational system in both countries and the profiles of their teachers and students.

I.1. The educational system of Burkina Faso

The educational system of Burkina Faso is a 3-6-4-3-3 divided into three different stages, basic education that encompasses preschool and primary education (3&6), secondary education which is made up of junior and senior schools (4&3) and higher education which is made of all post-secondary education (3 years for undergraduate studies). Students are respectively aged 3-5 years in Pre-primary, 6-11 years in Primary, 12-18 in Secondary, and 19-23 in Tertiary education (UNESCO, 2020). The age range is what it should be under normal circumstances. Pre-primary education is not well developed, and late schooling is common in primary education. A 2016 report on the educational system shows that children aged 7 or more represent 69% in the first grade in primary school. Families' poor socio-economic situation, the paucity of schools in remote areas are the main reasons behind late schooling. In 2014, the first stage of secondary (now call post-primary education) education has been linked to basic education to make compulsory education more pronounced. In fact, compulsory education goes until 16 years old.

Burkina Faso got a boost with the advent of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and now Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) which aim for quality and inclusive education for all with assistance from international partners such as Japan through its ambassador and JICA (Japan International Cooperation Agency), France through its embassy and AFD (*Agence Française de Développement*), the United States of America through its embassy and USAID (United States Aids for International Development), Germany, and more recently China. These partners help the country in capacity building by training key human resources in the educational systems, building schools and study abroad scholarships to help train in-service school personnel, governments of both countries strove to improve schooling rates with new policies and investments.

The combination of the international help and national efforts helped boost the educational system as many schools were built and the government has also recruited more teachers accordingly. This led to the improvement of schooling rates at the national level. The gross schooling rate increased from

77.4% in 2006/2007 to 97% in 2013/2014. The number of teachers and schools has tripled between 2001 and 2014.

These rates are not even because schools in remote areas or near mining sites struggle to keep students in classes, and this results in lots of dropouts. The challenges of dropouts lead to the loss of resources that were not even sufficient. Still, only 21% of the schooled children reach junior high school in 2006/2007 and 41.4% in 2013/2014 (MOE, Burkina Faso, 2018).

I.1.a. Primary education

Primary education is a standard level of six-year formal education, designed to provide basic information. It is designed for children 6 years of age and older and is the first level of compulsory education. It is sanctioned by a the *Certificat d'Etudes Primaires (CEP)* which can be translated as Certificate of Primary Education. According to Article 21 of the 2007 Act, basic education is compulsory, and it contains all the educational activities that take place in the school environment for the benefit of the 6- to 16-year-old children and primarily aimed to:

- (1) promote the development of the child's personality, skills, mental and physical abilities.
- (2) to instill in the child a sense of respect for the values of the Republic, including human rights and civil liberties.
- (3) Cultivate the child's sense of self-worth and respect for others, identity, language, cultural values, and national values.
- (4) prepare the child to take on the responsibilities of living in a free society, with a sense of understanding, peace, tolerance, gender equality and friendship among all people.
- (5) help the child understand the need for eco-citizenship.

Elementary education is divided into three 2-year cycles- The preparatory course (CP) which is the cycle of awakening. The elementary course (EC) which gives the child fundamental achievements that the average course (CM) will consolidate. The content and methods are tailored to the age of the children. Classes are taught in French (official language). Some national languages such as *mooré, dioula, fulfulde*, etc. were taught in bilingual schools, satellite schools and non-formal basic education centers (CEBNF). The CEBNEF (non-formal vocational schools designed for pre-16 children who dropped out or could not attend formal primary school) are now being formalized and the trainers more trained, organized and taken care by the national government instead of NGOs since 2016.

In addition, there are foreign language courses at the secondary level such as English in

secondary school curricula and taught throughout secondary education and German and/or Arabic, and Spanish taught from the 3rd year in lower secondary. The programs developed since 1989, largely inspired by those of 1962 but lightened, are presented over 24 weeks (about 660 hours per year) and included thirteen subjects. The emphasis is laid on the study of language. The schedule was as follows:

Table 1: Primary education: disciplines and weekly hours

Primary education: Study subjects weekly hours						
School disciplines	Number of minutes per week					
	Year1	Year	Year	Year	Year	Year
Plain talks	360	360	-	-	-	-
Writing	150	150	120	120	60	60
Counting	270	270	240	240	300	300
Sensory exercises	90	90	-	-	-	-
Poem and songs	120	120	90	90	120	120
Civic education	45	45	60	60	60	60
Speaking	-	-	60	60	60	60
Reading	420	420	420	420	240	240
Vocabulary	-	-	60	60	60	60
Grammar	-	-	60	60	60	60
Conjugation	-	-	60	60	60	60
Orthography	-	-	30	30	60	60
Short essays	-	-	60	60	180	180
Observation	-	-				
History and	-	-	90	90	120	120
Weekly total	1455	1455	1410	1410	1440	1440

Note: The school year is divided into 24 weeks of classes

I.1.b. Secondary education

After graduating from primary school, students can move on to the next level of secondary education, depending on the age and the grade the students got at the elementary school leaving certificate exam. Secondary education had a poor national coverage until 2014 when the junior schools was renamed post-primary education and built nationwide in almost every densely populated villages across the country. Secondary education is also on the rise, and vocational schools which were very limited are being built everywhere. Entry to secondary education has three age-related options: General education

option for children no more than 13 years old, vocational/technical Education option for children no more than 14 years old. Those aged 15 and above may not be granted entrance to public secondary schools. As far as general secondary education is concerned, in the first two years of the first cycle, the concepts acquired in primary education are reinforced, notably in French, History-Geography, Mathematics and Natural Sciences. English is introduced in the first year, and foreign languages other than English are introduced from the grade 3 in lower secondary. In the academic upper secondary, there are two possibilities for students: science related or and literary/arts-related options. The expositive method tends to take over from others because of the lack of resources required by science related classes such as Physics, Life Science, and Chemistry.

The school disciplines and national regulations apply to all schools in the national territory under the leadership of the Ministry of Education be it public or private schools. There are no subjects that are taught in one institution and that are not taught in another of the same nature and type. Students from the second Stage of Secondary education (High school students) are divided into different options – science-related option where Mathematics, Physics and Life Science are dominant, art-related option where Philosophy, Language Studies, and History are dominant, and vocational or technical options such as Clerical Studies, Accounting, Electricity, Mechanics, Building and Construction. Science oriented options are usually called long cycle and are expected to specialize at university. Technical and vocational studies students can look for a job after completing the CAP (Junior school leaving certificate for vocational and technical schools), the BEP (Professional certificate after two years in senior high school) or a professional or technical high school diploma when they complete the three years in Senior high school. However, in some exams (including baccalaureate), there are optional subjects that are not necessarily taught in the classroom (e.g., national languages). The following table summarizes the weekly hours for instruction in general secondary education (college and high school):

Table 2: Burkina Faso. General secondary education: weekly hours by teaching discipline: Lower secondary

Teaching disciplines	Year1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
German	–	–	3	3
English	5	5	3	3
French	7	7	5	5
History and Geography	3	3	3	3
Mathematics	5	5	5	5
Life science	3	3	3	4

Teaching disciplines	Year1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
Physics – chemistry	–	–	4	4
Physical education	2	2	2	2
Philosophy	–	–	–	–
Weekly total	25	25	28	29

Table 3: Burkina Faso. General secondary education: weekly hours by teaching disciplines: Upper Secondary

	Year 1	Year 1	Year 2	Year 2	Year 2	Year 3	Year 3	Year 3
	A	C	A	C	D	A	C	D
German	6	–	6	–	–	5	–	–
English	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
French	5	5	5	4	4	5	4	4
History and Mathematics	3	3	3	3	3	4	3	3
Mathematics	3	5	3	7	6	3	9	6
Life science	2	3	2	2	4	–	3	6
Physics - chemistry	3	6	2	6	5	–	6	5
Physical education	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Philosophy	–	–	3	2	2	8	3	3
Weekly total	27	27	29	29	29	30	33	32

Note: A refers to literary/art related major and C and refers to Science related majors. C is when Mathematics and Physics are the dominant discipline and D is when Life Science and Maths are the dominant disciplines.

I.2. The educational system of Japan

The current Japanese education system is 3-6-3-3-4 divided into the following categories - kindergarten, elementary school, primary school, junior school (middle school/lower secondary), high school (upper secondary), and higher education which is composed of undergraduate and graduate education. Compulsory education continues until 15 years old, that is until junior school.

The Japanese educational system has a long history as it changed along the historical landmark of Japan. At the end of the *Shunagate*, education differed according to the social strata. One noticeable feature of the royal society of the Edo period was the traditional division of classes into samurai,

farmers, artisans, and merchants with a particularly strong distinction between the Samurai and the rest of the structure. This fact reflected all the social and cultural life of the Edo period. In the field of education, separate schools were designed for each social stratum. - the fief schools (*hanko* or *hangaku*) for the samurai and the *terakoya* for the commoners (MEXT, 2020).

During the Edo period, Japan limited its cooperation with the outside world. The small gate way to the foreign world has been critical to the modernization of Japan as they learnt western medicine, Dutch language, and later English toward the end of the Edo period. The first reason for learning was simply curiosity, and the second reason was a desire to learn about Western military strategy and technology. This gave way to the modernization of Japan during the Restoration period and the dualistic educational system began to crumble (Mext, 2020).

The scrambling of the dualistic system was made easy when Japan found it necessary to adapt to the outside world as the small window on the West during the self-isolation brought valuable benefits to the country in the field of medicine and military. The *Empero's* 5-article Oath April 6, 1868 marked the start of modern Education in Japan. Article 3 sealed the end of the dualistic system. It states that Article 3 stated that, "All classes of people shall be allowed to fulfill their just aspirations so that there may be no discontent." But it was not until 1871 when the fief was abolished that the new government had full control of the educational system, created schools in the prefectures and opened elementary schools for all the children of Japan regardless of their social status. In 1872, the first elementary school under the direct governance of the new Meiji government, Spelling, calligraphy, words pronunciation, arithmetic, oral instruction in morals and words recitation were to be taught for the first semester, and many Western-based diversity subjects would be gradually introduced as students progressed to higher levels; textbooks categorized by form. In 1873, a revision was made to offer "the nine subjects of reading, arithmetic, calligraphy, dictation, composition, oral lessons (*mondo*), reading comprehension, comprehensive review and physical education. Special attention was given to reading, arithmetic, calligraphy, and oral lessons (MEXT, 2020).

I.2.a. Elementary education

In the Japanese education system, it is first thought that all children have the same ability to read and master the school curriculum. A second thought is that certain habits and traits, such as diligence and attention, can be taught. In view of the fact that all children have equal abilities, different outcomes in student achievement are thought to be due to different efforts, patience, perseverance, and self-discipline. Besides progression to the next grade is automatic regardless of academic achievement.

Even though differentiated instruction is widely not used, teachers are encouraged to take care of students with low achievements.

The classroom teacher instructs proper behavior and classroom routines first graders during the first weeks of school to lay foundation for desirable attitudes and habits which are expected throughout the child's school life. Japanese elementary school students' attention centers around the teacher and the textbook and they learn to take notes in the 1st grade. Written tests are provided regularly, and homework is provided on a regular basis, and teachers are required to cover all the material that the course of study mandates for each grade level. It is important to know that the Japanese consider science and mathematics to be the building blocks of technology, and curriculum requirements ensure that all children receive a solid foundation in those disciplines throughout elementary and secondary education. The school subjects also referred as school curriculum for Japanese elementary schools can be found in table 4 below.

Table 4: Elementary School's Curriculum

	1 st grade	2 nd grade	3 rd grade	4 th grade	5 th grade	6 th grade
Japanese Language Arts	9	9	7	7	6	6
Social Studies			3	3	4	4
Mathematics	5	5	5	5	5	
Science			3	3	3	3
Life Environment Studies	3	3				
Foreign language	10	10	10	10	10	10
Music	2	2	2	2	2	2
Arts and Crafts	2	2	2	2	2	2
Home Economics						
Physical Education	3	3	2	2	2	2
Moral education						
Special Activities	School Event, Field Trip, and Moral Education					
Comprehensive Learning						
Weekly total	34	34	34	34	34	34
Yearly total (Public schools) in Japanese-coined	850	910	945	980	980	980

Source: Adapted from Japanese Children's society,

I.2.b. Middle school

After ending the dualistic educational system, Japan continued the reforms to middle Schools Where It first approved sixteen study subjects in the lower division including Japanese Language, Science,

Drawing, the Classics, Geometry, Bookkeeping, Natural History, Mathematics, Calligraphy, Chemistry, Morals, Archeology, Geometry, Bookkeeping, Geography, History, Foreign Languages, Science, Painting, Surveying and Western Music. In the upper division of middle school, 15 subjects were approved. This curriculum included Japanese language, Mathematics, Calligraphy, Foreign Languages, Science, Mechanical Drawing, The Classics, Algebra & Geometry, Bookkeeping, Chemistry, Morals, Surveying, Economics, Mechanics (*Jugaku*), and Zoology, Botany, Geology & Mining. (Mext 2020)

As in Burkina Faso, each class has its own room where it remains all day and teachers move between classrooms. The room, and its daily maintenance, is the responsibility of the students. (This is also the situation at the upper secondary level.) Each class is assigned an advisor, *tannin*, whose duties are same as those of an educator in the case of Burkina Faso. Unlike Burkina Faso where the educator does not have teaching duties, the *tannin* is a teacher who is responsible for the “academic and social guidance of the members of the class, including counseling on personal and behavioral problems”. At the end of the middle school, the *tannin* guides students in choosing the most appropriate upper secondary school.

As far as instruction is concerned, students are taught and evaluated in Japanese secondary education and high school and university entrance examinations based on the premise that there is only one correct answer based on premium mastery of factual material, often through drill and memorization, rather than on analysis, investigation, and critical thinking. Japanese instruction is heavily based on lectures which in-turn adheres closely to the textbook specified by the Ministry of Education and teachers are often desperate to cover the prescribed material thoroughly in a teacher-centered style and memorization. However, field trips, student projects, and laboratory work in science are other instructions that are used. Likewise, elementary school, students are treated uniformly and are not assigned to separate classes or groups based on ability.

In addition to the required subjects of the core curriculum, the lower secondary school introduces the study of English. The typical number of class periods per week for the full curriculum is shown in table 2. Nowadays, the approved curriculum for lower secondary school is found in table 5.

Table 5: Junior school Curriculum

Disciplines	1 st year	2 nd year	3 rd year
Japanese Language Arts	140	105	105
Social studies	105	105	85
Mathematics	105	105	105

Disciplines	1 st year	2 nd year	3 rd year
Science	105	105	85
Music	45	35	35
Art	45	35	35
Physical Education	90	90	90
Industrial Arts and Home Economics	70	70	35
Foreign Language	105	105	105
Moral Education	35	35	35
Special activities	35	35	35
Elective subjects	0-30	50-85	105-165
Comprehensive Learning and Activities	70-100	70-105	70-130
Total class hours	980	980	980

Source: Ishikida, M. Y. (2005) adapted by author

I.2.c. Senior High School

Unlike middle school where the school subjects are the same for all the students, Japanese upper secondary school students take the same classes in year 1 only. For Year 2 and 3, Japanese high school students attend either an academic or a vocational course of study. The academic program prepares students for college. In the second and third years in academic programs, students choose to specialize either in literature or science. The ministry of education requires that about one-third of student time be devoted to vocational education in the second and third year of the program and the second half will be spent on general education. Even though vocational school prepares students with lifelong skills, they remain less dominant as compared to academic courses. Free and compulsory education ends in middle school. Therefore, both private and public upper secondary school charge tuition and supplementary charges such as supplementary books, *juku* (private tutoring) tuition, or private tutoring costs. Tables 5, 6, 7 show the different school disciplines in each of the three years in upper secondary academic programs.

Table 6: Weekly hours in upper secondary academic programs: first year

All Students	Weekly Hours
Japanese I	5
Contemporary Society	4
Mathematics I	6
Science I	4
English I	6

All Students	Weekly Hours
Physical Education and	
Home economics*	4
Health	1
Music or Calligraphy	2
Homeroom	1
Club activities	1
Total class hours per week	34

Source: Adapted from Japanese Children's Society

Table 7: Weekly hours in upper secondary academic programs: Second year

Literature Majors	Weekly	Weekly	Science Majors
Japanese II	5	4	Japanese II
Classical Literature	2	3	Japanese History or World History
Japanese History	2	3	Algebra & Geometry
World History	3	3	Basic Mathematical Analysis
Basic Mathematical Analysis	3	4	Physics
Biology or Chemistry	3	4	Chemistry
English	7	5	English
Physical Education & Home economics*	4	4	Physical Education & Home economics*
Health	1	1	Health
Music or Calligraphy	2	1	Music or Calligraphy
Homeroom	1	1	Homeroom
Club activities	1	1	Club activities
Total class hours per week	34	34	Total class hours per week

Source: Adapted from Japanese Children's Society

*Boys take 4 hours of physical education and girls take 2 hours and 2 hours of home economics.

Table 8: Weekly hours in upper secondary academic programs: Third year

Literature Majors	Weekly	Weekly	Science Majors
Modern Literature	4	3	Modern Literature
Classical Literature	4	2	Japanese History or World History
Japanese History	3	5	Integral and Differential Calculus
World History	3		
Ethics or Politics	3	5	Probability and statistics
Basic Mathematical Analysis	2	4	Physics
Biology or Chemistry	2	4	Chemistry
English	8	6	English
Physical Education	3	3	Physical Education
Homeroom	1	1	Homeroom
Club activities	1	1	Club activities
Total class hours per week	34	34	Total class hours per week

Source: Adapted from Japanese Children's Society

I.3. Students' profiles in Burkina Faso and Japan

I.3.a. Students' profiles in Burkina Faso

In Burkina Faso, kindergarten students are 3-5 years old. Primary education lasts for 6 years and students are between the ages of 6-12 under normal circumstances but due to late schooling, 69% of the students are more the normal age when they enter primary school (MOE, Burkina Faso, 2018). This late schooling also impacts the age of students throughout the educational system. Secondary education is divided into stages, lower secondary education is 4 years and students graduate with the BEPC if they attended a general education school or the CAP (delivered after 3 years of studies in a vocational school) while attending a technical or vocational school. In upper secondary education, students choose either the science-oriented section or art-oriented to continue their education. Students from vocational schools can continue with their training in an upper vocational/technical secondary school. It is important to note that after graduating from lower secondary school, students can switch to vocational or general upper secondary education depending on their grades on the different core subjects in the desired option.

After three years in upper secondary education, students take the *baccalauréat* exam (the national exam to graduate from upper secondary equivalent to the high school diploma or A Level Exam) in

their option. Passing the *baccalauréat* gives students the opportunity to automatically access higher education and are placed in different department at different universities according to their choices and performances at the exam. From there, it normally takes three years to get a *Licence* (bachelor's degree). Students with better grades can further their studies in graduate schools where one needs to apply and take an entrance examination or ranked according to the grades in the undergraduate studies along with other applicants. Vocational school students also take the *baccalauréat* exam in their field and can also go to university or look for a job. Unlike students from vocational schools who are not numerous, students from general education still need further training in a specific field to work.

1.3.b. Students' profiles in Burkina Faso and Japan

Japanese children start kindergarten at the age of 3 and enter primary school in the month of April (the new school year starts in April in Japan) following their 6th birthday. Then they spend 3 years in Junior high school where compulsory education ends. Then, students go on to high school for three years. They can join a vocational school or join a more academic program where they specialize in literature or science as seen in table 6,7,8 on pages 12-13. Those who opted for the academic programs in either literature or science graduate with a *High School Certificate of Graduation* and those from vocational high school, a *Specialized Training Schools Upper Secondary Certificate of Graduation*. However, after junior school, some student can join a different type of school (Junior colleges) where they spend five years and graduate with an Associate Degree. They can get a bachelor's degree by joining an undergraduate program where they will spend 2 more years.

I.4 Teachers' profiles in Burkina Faso and Japan

I.4.a. Teachers' profiles in Burkina Faso

Burkina Faso has training schools for primary school teachers. In Burkina Faso, teachers were trained for two years at the *Ecole Nationale des Enseignants du Primaire* (ENEP) where they graduate with *the Diplôme de Fin d'Etudes de l'ENEP* (DEFENEP), a teaching diploma. Some of them also graduate from private training institutions with a *Certificat Élémentaire d'Aptitude Pédagogique* (CEAP). The basic degree was the *Brevet d'Etude du Premier Cycle* (BEPC) (lower secondary school graduation certificate) until 2020 when they changed to *the Baccalauréat*, the upper secondary School leaving diploma. Both teachers for the ENEP and the private training Institutions have two years of theoretical training and one year of practical training in schools under the supervision of experienced teachers and teacher trainers. After the initial training, teachers can sit for a certification exam after teaching for at least five years. Their colleagues of secondary schools are recruited among university graduates.

As of 2020, secondary school teachers are recruited among people with at least a bachelor's degree in the subject they intend to teach. Then, they are sent to the teacher-training college for a two-year training – one year for theoretical classes and the second year in a classroom with the help of experienced teachers and an inspector of the same subject. Prior to this, Junior school teachers were recruited with the Associate degree and sent to the teacher-training college for 2 years. Some were recruited with the *Baccalauréat* and sent to a teacher-training college for 4 years. After the initial teacher training, there are some professional development programs for teachers.

In Burkina Faso teachers benefit from in-service and capacity-building programs where they learn from their peers and learned people in teaching and pedagogy such as advisors, inspectors, and educational researchers. There used to be "*Groupe d'Animation Pédagogique*" i.e Pedagogical Animation Group (PAG) where primary school teachers of a given department convene to learn and update their knowledge. The Pedagogical Animation Group is a framework for continuing education, self-training, exchange of experiences and information, for teachers of primary schools and *CEBNF: Centre d'Education de Base Non-Formelle* (CEBNF can be translated as Non-formal Basic Education Centers. The aim is to share knowledge and empower teachers, able to promote education, discuss and influence its quality for the benefit of the society. It consisted of a minimum of 15 teachers and a maximum of forty-five (45) teachers. The grouping was conducted primarily based on geographical proximity, five (05) to eight (08) times during the school year and rotating from one school to another and was led by a coordinator appointed by the district chief. Its organization and operation were governed by Act No. 2008/0083/MEBA/SG/DGEB/DDEB of 08 June 2008. There were Pedagogical animation groups (GAP) in all district of basic education.

Means back led the ministry of education to suspend the PAG and teachers now convene yearly to debate main educational issues per region known as "*Conférence annuelle*". Likewise, secondary education teachers also benefit from on-the-job training to refine their knowledge to adapt to the ever-changing teaching practices, paradigms and approaches to learning.

The Ministry of Education strives to meet Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 4 which is to ensure inclusive and quality education of all school-going children regardless of socio-economic background or special need. The various annual conferences and other in-service training are of a larger effort on diverse topic to ensure quality and reach the educational objectives.

Class management, lesson planning, and other topics are discussed during the annual conferences. The head of each conference at the education district level is free to add secondary topics according to the priorities in his district. Thus, from one education district to another, we have a diversity of subtopics

ranging from conjugation to inclusive education through innovative approaches in the education system. In short, topics that range from applied pedagogy to ongoing innovations in the education system and teachers leave annual conferences with solid gains in terms of classroom management.

I.4.b. Teachers' profiles in Japan

Becoming a teacher in Japan is very selective, especially in the recruitment phase. You make the cut only after going through series of rigorous exams and assessments by the school board.

First, teachers must have a university degree. Degrees are conferred any university, including junior colleges that can offer teacher training courses that are approved by the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sport, Science and Technology (MEXT). Potential teachers take the National Center's university admissions test to be considered for admission to a primary school teacher training program. In addition to the national examination, some national universities often carry out their own examinations. During training, prospective teachers take courses in both their subject areas and pedagogy and they are assessed by an experienced teacher under the supervision of a headteacher. After completing a teacher training program, teachers must complete a teaching internship for at least three weeks.

Despite the selective nature of the teaching profession, teacher supply exceeds demand. After completing their teacher training courses, applicants must pass a recruitment test, which is supervised by the prefectural authority. In addition, prefectural education committees typically require a prospective teacher to pass aptitude tests, interviews or essays and examine the pedagogical and technical knowledge of the applicant. The interviews usually include a demonstration lesson where the applicant can use integrated teaching skills. Requirements vary by prefecture. After passing the exam, the applicants are ranked in a registration according to their scores. The top candidates are hired first and candidates who are not recruited must repeat the exam the following year. In 2013, nearly one in five teacher candidates who passed the employment exam for teachers in public schools were hired as teachers, making recruitment as a teacher very competitive. There are virtually no classes taught by teachers who do not have a certificate in their field of study or subject. There are also no alternative ways to get into the teaching profession (NCEE, n. d.).

Once teachers have been hired, they go through a one-year induction period. During this time, they are supervised by a senior teacher who acts as a mentor. Both the new teacher and the mentor are given fewer teaching responsibilities so that they can work together on lesson management, teaching strategies and techniques, lesson planning and analysis. The choice of mentors varies from prefecture to prefecture and even from school to school. Mentors receive neither special training nor additional

pay. New teachers are first put on probation. At the end of the first year, a teacher can be hired as a full-time regular teacher and has access to all teacher benefits, including membership of the teachers' union. Most Japanese teachers remain in the profession until retirement.

In the teaching profession, continuous professional development is required. Vocational development programs are offered at national level at school level and each local school authority determines the minimum hours that a teacher must spend each year on professional development.

In addition to formal vocational development programs, Japanese teachers learn informally from their colleagues.

In Japan, there is a teaching culture, where teachers meet to evaluate and improve their practice, including errors analysis. This traditional profession development is attended by hundreds of teachers, researchers, and policy makers with the aim to improve teaching quality, share experience and learn from each other about better practices. This traditional approach is called *jogyokenkyu* meaning lesson study (Fernandez, 2002)

The study of the lesson is called in Japanese *Jogyokenkyu*, *jogyo* meaning lesson and *kenkyu* study or research. More than a study of lessons, it is a kind of formal review of teaching practices. Teachers begin their lessons by setting a goal for themselves during the meeting. For instance, they may decide that students will be more involved in peer-to-peer math learning. They then begin to study lessons to explore instructional strategies that help achieve this goal. Teachers develop meticulous planning in the form of a writing. Then, one of the teachers implements it with his students while the other members of the group observe the situation while taking notes. Then they reconvene to discuss their observations and share their opinions. They may approve the strategies or lesson plans used choose to revise the lesson by creating a new planning with new strategies. Then, another teacher who embarks on the exploration under the observation of his colleagues. This activity requires approximately 10 to 15 hours of group meetings over a period of 3 to 4 weeks. Large groups are divided into groups of four to six teachers.

The report on the lesson study meeting is published in the form of a "newsletter" describing the work done as well as the common reflections, but also the innovations and improvements made. This activity is followed by the Ministry of Education and its regional offices, which can finance some or all of these experiments. Institutions working under its guidelines are equated with "research institutions" (*Kenkyushiteiko*) and contribute to influencing the direction of Japanese education policy. This formal recognition, along with the interest of teachers in primary and secondary schools, make

these studies highly prized in Japan, and they constitute an important part of the initial and continuing training of teachers.

For a teacher it is therefore customary to be involved in a group at the level of his educational unit and to be attached to a regional group where multiple experiences are shared. Often, an external advisor helps these different groups observe and comment on the lessons they have planned. These counsellors are erudite with extensive knowledge of pedagogical and disciplinary issues and can mobilize theoretical and methodological knowledge useful to teachers. The role of the counsellor should be limited to accompaniment without taking charge of the study itself, which remains the property of the teachers. Educational units organize a kind of "open door" operations where they invite teachers and other educators to discuss and exchange on the results of a particular study. Schools with a good reputation attract many colleagues, sometimes hundreds from across the country. Reports or bulletins on lessons circulate between teachers and education officials: they are disseminated through the network of booksellers and constitute a large part of the research literature read by Japanese teachers.

CHAPTER II. CURRICULUM: DEFINITION, THEORY, AND PRACTICE

Educational policies follow some theories and pattern or intermingle different theories or in-between. These theories are based on beliefs and values, tested, experimented, and assessed. These policies are translated into course of study i.e. curriculum which is then delivered in classroom setting through instruction. This chapter deals with the definition of curriculum, its theory and practice.

II.1. Defining curriculum

Before defining the term curriculum, it is very important to define Education and relate to the curriculum to see how they fit together. The definition of education differs from one scholar to another in the same field. Nyagah G. (2010) describes education as the process of acquiring the desired knowledge, skills, and attitudes to become an active member of society. The word education means “drawing”, which means helping learners to discover their potential and latent abilities. To achieve this "drawing" of students, the teacher turns to the curriculum so that learners unleash their full potential. What activities does education accomplish?

It has a variety of functions including the following: - Intellectual function. This is done so that men can awaken and have a taste of knowledge. It develops the mental capacity of students. - Productive function that provides people with information, skills, and attitudes that can be used for economic activities in society. Vocational training contributes to this function. - Social function which in this context, education is seen as a process of preserving and passing on cultural heritage. Apart from education, it helps learners to acquire interpersonal skills. Education is also a way for individual development. So does personal work (Nyagah, 2010).

The term "curriculum" comes from the Greek word "*curere*" which means "to run a course". Scholar still has different definitions of the term "curriculum". These divisive ideas are due to the position or approach of scholars or the basis of philosophy or universal understanding, often referred to as "complicated conversations" (Pinar, 2012) which should not only be the concerns of curriculum theorist but to “who is able to participate in the conversation, how that conversation is referenced, the degree of coherence within the conversation, and the value and function of the conversation” (Herbert et al, 2019: 06).

Although there is no standard / general definition of the curriculum, various scholars have defined it according to their philosophical or contextual aspirations. Curriculum definition set on a continuum from narrow to broad focus. One narrow focus defines curriculum as a course of study or learning

program. In a broader sense, however, the curriculum is based on all that happens during the planning, teaching, and learning of the institution (Oliva, 1997; Derebssa, 2004).

In addition, the broader approach to curriculum, non-technical, and more philosophical, personal, and interesting, includes a wide range of ideas and perspectives. The curriculum includes educational objectives and plans. Curriculum covers beliefs, values, attitudes, skills, knowledge and all aspects of education. One may wonder how if possible, formal education can be without a curriculum. It is for this reason that academics such as Print (1993) refer to the curriculum as the educational motto, the very object of learning.

Burkina Faso is a developing country that needs to accelerate its development. Therefore, there is an urgent need to rethink the education system through the school curriculum evaluation and revision. It can start by defining curriculum as a plan, set of plans, a blueprint to guide the educational system and actors, a guide for teaching/learning to bring about positive and desirable change in student behavior and develop their abilities. Offorma (2016) states that curriculum is a reliable tool for achieving national education goals. Education is the source of all the benefits of development in any country. Values and cultural structures are critical factors to consider when embarking on a school curriculum adaptation to suit the developmental needs of the community for which it is designed. In the same vein, Offorma (2016: 3) states that the curriculum can continue to be regarded as a tool in which schools strive to translate the needs and aspirations of the communities in which they operate into a reality. To achieve this, there is a need for an inclusive approach to bring together all the different groups involved in the development process in order to have a good combination. In this regard, one could argue that curriculum planning, as well as curriculum development, should involve all stakeholders in education. This means that it must take into account the needs of employers, parents, students' career goals, and the skills that society needs to achieve the various goals contained in the various development programs. It should encompass all that will make students functional members of society. Offorma (2016: 4) summed up the idea when he said that the curriculum "should be a reflection of what people do, feel, and believe".

Print (1993) defines curriculum as all the planned learning opportunities offered to students by the educational institution and the experiences that students experience when using the curriculum. It is a whole range of experiences, aimed at and not directed, that are involved in revealing a person's skills.

Table 9: A table summarizing some Prescriptive Definitions of Curriculum

Date	Author	Definition
1902	John Dewey	Curriculum is a continuous reconstruction, moving from the child's present experience out into that represented by the organized bodies of truth that we call studies. . . . the various studies . . . are themselves experience— they are that of the race. (pp. 11–12)
1918	Franklin Bobbitt	Curriculum is the entire range of experiences, both directed and undirected, concerned in unfolding the abilities of the individual (p.43)
1927	Harold O. Rugg	[The curriculum is] a succession of experiences and enterprises having a maximum lifelikeness for the learner . . . giving the learner that development most helpful in meeting and controlling life situations. (p. 8)
1935	Hollis Caswell in Caswell & Campbell	The curriculum is composed of all the experiences children have under the guidance of teachers Thus, curriculum considered as a field of study represents no strictly limited body of content, but rather a process or procedure. (pp. 66, 70)
1957	Ralph Tyler	[The curriculum is] all the learning experiences planned and directed by the school to attain its educational goals. (p. 79)
1967	Robert Gagne	Curriculum is a sequence of content units arranged in such a way that the learning of each unit may be accomplished as a single act, provided the capabilities described by specified prior units (in the sequence) have already been mastered by the learner. (p. 23)
1970	James Popham & Eva Baker	[Curriculum is] all planned learning outcomes for which the school is responsible. Curriculum refers to the desired consequences of instruction. (p. 48)
1997	J. L. McBrien & R. Brandt	[Curriculum] refers to a written plan outlining what students will be taught (a course of study). Curriculum may refer to all the courses offered at a given school, or all the courses offered at a school in a particular area of study.
2010	Indiana Department of Education	Curriculum means the planned interaction of pupils with instructional content, materials, resources, and processes for evaluating the attainment of educational objectives. (n.p.)

Sources: Glatthorn, A. A., Boschee, F., Whitehead, B. M., & Boschee, B. F. (2018).

Table 10: A table summarizing some Prescriptive Definitions of Curriculum

Date	Author	Definition
1935	Hollis Caswell & Doak Campbell	All the experiences children have under the guidance of teachers.
1941	Thomas Hopkins	Those learnings each child selects, accepts, and incorporates into himself to act with, on, and upon, in subsequent experiences.
1960	W. B. Ragan	All experiences of the child for which the school accepts responsibility.
1987	Glen Hass	The set of actual experiences and perceptions of the experiences that each individual learner has of his or her program of education.
1995	Daniel Tanner & Laurel Tanner	The reconstruction of knowledge and experience that enables the learner to grow in exercising intelligent control of subsequent knowledge and experience.
2006	D. F. Brown	All student school experiences relating to the improvement of skills and strategies in thinking critically and creatively, solving problems, working collaboratively with others, communicating well, writing more effectively, reading more analytically, and conducting research to solve problems.
2009	E. Silva	An emphasis on what students can do with knowledge, rather than what units of knowledge they have, is the essence of 21st-century skills.

Sources: Glatthorn, A. A., Boschee, F., Whitehead, B. M., & Boschee, B. F. (2018).

Curriculum is the backbone of education... [and] is a specific, tangible subject that is always linked to institutional decision-making (Null 2011, 2016). Curriculum is not always a popular educational issue, but the curriculum is involved in educational decision-making, whether it relates to the allocation of funds, skills, standards, limited assessment, or new curriculum adoption. It is for this reason that we need to look at the teaching and practice of the curriculum today. Curriculum is all learning, planned and directed by the school, whether done in groups or individually, inside or outside the school (Kelly, 1999) or “the planned interaction of pupils with instructional content, materials, resources, and processes for evaluating the attainment of educational objectives” (Indiana Department of Education quoted in Glatthorn, A. A., Boschee, F., Whitehead, B. M., & Boschee, B. F 2018: 4)

II.2. Curriculum theories

The diverging viewpoint on the definition of curriculum are also reflected on curriculum theories. In the same vein, Morrison (2007) is of the opinion that the debate on curriculum should go beyond curriculum theorists and the academics as opposed to Wraga and Hlebowitsh (2003) who proposed a delineating the field of curriculum after a thorough account of the crisis in the field of curriculum from the 1920 to the 21st century based on curriculum crisis as identified by Schwab in 1969. Morrison (2007) argues that: Curriculum theory is moribund, with its graffiti often engraved with a fan cabal and its sacred texts of a different hue, and trade in a few well-twisted phrases. How often does curriculum theory in this subject include research of the ideas set forth, set texts, and authors, in alphabetical order: Apple, Bruner, Dewey, Doll, Giroux, Ornstein, Pinar, Tanner, Tyler, and so on? Well, everyone deserves it, but is this enough? See descriptions that take place in curriculum papers. Do scientists or economists still argue or refer to their theoretical principles fifty years ago? We need an adult party; the field of curriculum theory should be developed or discarded in the infinite childhood of existing discipline. And how should it grow? I suggest that curriculum theory should come out of the edge of the educational institution. He or she must enter a tertiary institution but must pass. If the curriculum becomes a curriculum compliant, then it will be discarded. It is as if religion should be reserved for theologians only or that food should be reserved for cooks only. The concept of the curriculum is not hagiography. Just as the saying goes that when a topic is politically sensitive, it should not be left to politicians more, so as the discussion of subject theory grows, it should not be left to curriculum educators. Democracy requires that the repetition of words be heard in academic matters.

Debate on ideas and curriculum practices is not a major concern for this paper, not because it is inappropriate but there is an urgent need to help Burkina Faso in its studies strive to find appropriate education policies and content topics to align educational content, familiarize the labor market as the education system. Therefore, many graduates are waiting to enter the public service to do normal work, but the country needs qualifications that not only create jobs but also have the potential to prepare for new social and economic changes and the changing needs of the labor market. Therefore, this paper will be interested in going through a four-way curriculum approach based on Kelly (1999) where the curriculum incorporates structured and directed learning.

Curriculum as process means that the curriculum is dynamic and flexible depending on how it was planned and conducted, with whom and where. It means communication between teachers and students. This means that the curriculum is what happens in a set classroom and what the teacher does to prepare and evaluate. This type of curriculum focuses on the classroom teacher.

Curriculum as praxis refers to the planning of educational content. Similarly, curriculum processing is the responsibility of teachers and they have the same influence on the learning process (Smith, 1996, 2000). That is, the curriculum in this context is not just a set of strategies to be used, but a practical process in which planning, implementation, and evaluation are all integrated and integrated into the process (Grundy 1987). This type of curriculum develops a particular dynamic and attributes an interrelationship between teachers and students in explaining the meaning, learning, and teaching processes in educational institutions in educational institutions.

A curriculum as product refers to a set of information for the practical purpose of creating an educational, comprehensive, or specific system that reflects values and environmental guidance and achieves certain objectives. Therefore, it has a proprietary nature and plays an important role because it tends to press the project and is linearized and descending. Therefore, this type of program can lead to failure because it does not involve students throughout the process (Mile, 2005; Depover & Jonnaert, 2014). This type of curriculum sets the required behaviors and established norms that a student is expected to have. Students from these types of subjects often show similar characteristics because of the way the curriculum is structured.

Curriculum as content refers to a set of activities that should be carried out. Contrary to what we have seen in the previous three sections of the curriculum, the curriculum, discusses the relationship between objectives and tools. However, the information here is not intended to be intended but merely a method used. This type of curriculum is usually equivalent to a syllabus. In addition to these approaches, Null (2011, 2016) states that there are five (05) traditional curriculum practices in education today and each has a role to play in addressing the curriculum problems of the time-systematic, - existentialist, -radical, - pragmatic and - deliberative curriculum.

Systematic approach to curriculum development is divided into five steps: 1) conducting needs assessment, 2) defining learning objectives 3) identifying resources, 4) developing educational strategies and implementing the curriculum, and 5) evaluating and adapting curriculum.

Existentialist curriculum aims to produce independent students and help them to make their own choices and thus develop personality among students. The curriculum is about teaching a variety of subjects in art, science, and humanity but with a strong focus on humanity because the education of all human beings is represented by the individual. Existentialism proposes a child-centered approach that will be used as a classroom teaching method. Complete freedom is granted to the student under the guidance of the teacher. The teacher is the backbone of the entire education system. As a guide the

teacher should help students to understand students' independence. The teacher does not make rules or make jokes, demean the students, or demean the students.

Radical curriculum theory “privileges some form of participatory democracy both in schools and in the wider social sphere. The debates over definitions, however, are couched in such a manner as to exclude the negotiations necessary for their implementation in the public sphere” (Deever, 1996:257).

Pragmatic curriculum is about integrating of subjects and activities. According to pragmatism knowledge is one unit. Pragmatists want to create a flexible, dynamic, and integrated curriculum that helps the child development and a more flexible society as needs, change and circumstances require.

Deliberated curriculum is a form of academic inquiry where teachers, students, communities, and authorities identify and explain curricular problems in contexts, design and explore possible solutions, evaluate their alternatives, and decide the course of actions to address the issues (Null, 2011,2017; W. A. Reid; Schwab, 1973). Englund (2006) notes that a strength of deliberative curriculum is that it helps identify the issue; an integral first step in finding a solution is the identification of the problem/issue needs to be addressed in the first place and defining it clearly.

II.3. Curriculum practice: Society, curriculum, and instruction

When we define culture as a way of thinking and the knowledge base and curriculum as a curriculum, there is a need to adapt the curriculum to the intended community. This adjustment means that we need to integrate the knowledge base and thinking strategies into the process of building the curriculum. According to Offorma (2016) integration means that what is given to a school must be in line with what the community needs. In content planning and learning experiences (teaching method), integration refers to the horizontal relationship of curriculum content and learning experiences.

The inclusion of cultural elements in the school curriculum is a strategy to close what is taught in the school and what students feel in their life or community in order to unite students as active members of society. Curriculum integration will be achieved if the school curriculum reflects the culture of the community and its needs. Therefore, curriculum planners should link the content and experience of the curriculum with human cultures. To achieve this, we need to answer the following questions: "What should be taught, to whom, under what circumstances, how, and in what sense? and What processes should we use to determine what our curriculum should be within a particular school, college, or university (Null 2011, 2016)?

Research shows that cultural factors should be considered when planning or designing a school curriculum. A given community curriculum should incorporate this specialty to make sense in the community, making students active members of the community at the end of a particular cycle. This is a real way for the community to take ownership of formal education because it will showcase its pricing system and offer new ideas to improve its scope of action. According to Goff (1998) everyone involved in this problem needs to be involved in the solution. This is an integral part of the negotiation process - including parents, teachers, students, administrators, and community members in debating and deciding the curriculum.

Instruction involves conveying knowledge, developing skills and attitudes, and responding to specific needs in a variety of ways ranging from formal to diverse activities, including educational support activities that help and improve the learning-learning process. It can be transmitted to the classroom through lectures, repetitions, or access to technology services. Therefore, teaching can be defined as the process of teaching, bringing the curriculum, and creating learning environments for students.

Although the curriculum and instruction are linked to each other, it is not the same and at the same time, one cannot talk about it without referring to the curriculum. We can easily look at the curriculum as what is being taught and the instructions as to how it is taught. Simply put, curriculum can be called "what" and instruction as "how". Therefore, curriculum can be viewed as a program, content, and learning experience, while instruction as methods, teaching, initiation, and presentation. There are four (04) different types of curriculum-instruction relationships included such as (1) dualistic model, (2) connection model, (3) focus model, and (4) rotation model (Derebssa, 2004).

Dualistic Model - Curriculum and instruction are two independent entities that are both intertwined but have never merged. Therefore, there is a gap between these two entities, and what happens in the classroom under the teacher's guidance seems to be cut off from the master plan. The curriculum planners ignore instructors who in turn ignore them. Curriculum theories are different from practice and use in the classroom. Under this model, the curriculum and teaching process can change without affecting each other significantly.

Interlocking models - In this model, the curriculum and instruction are intertwined and there is a playful/connected relationship between them. This model does not give precedence to one over the other and no matter which one comes first or appears left or right. This model relationship clearly illustrates the interconnected relationship between the two organizations. Therefore, isolating one can be very damaging to both.

Concentric Model - In this model, instruction may seem to be the bottom line of a curriculum or curriculum a sub-system of instruction. This model demonstrates the interdependence between the curriculum and the teaching of various sequential/varying relationships.

Cyclical Models - Curriculum-instruction relationships are a simplified model of the system that emphasizes the essence of feedback. Curriculum and instruction are different things that have a continuous cyclical relationship. The curriculum has a continuing impact on instruction and, conversely, instruction has an impact on the curriculum. The cyclical model means that the curricular decisions are made after the pedagogical decisions, which are changed after the implementation and evaluation of the pedagogical decisions. The process continues, repeats, and never ends. Assessment of teaching methods affects the next round of decision-making in the curriculum, which in turn affects the implementation of teaching. While the curriculum and rules appear to be different with this model it should not be conceived as an independent entity but as part of a phase - a circular circle, which creates continuous flexibility and development of the two entities.

CHAPTER III. EDUCATIONAL POLICIES AND CLASSROOM INSTRUCTION

Some political authorities usually decide educational policies based on their agenda and political views leaving out educational researchers and practitioners in the decision process. This often results in failures as actors of the implementation commonplaces might not have clear guidance on the way to go about it. Successful implementations result from careful planning with all the different expertise. This chapter deals with the overview of educational policies in Burkina Faso and Japan and how they are implemented in classrooms.

III.1. Educational policies and national curriculum of Burkina Faso

Since independence in 1960, Burkina Faso (formerly Upper Volta) has undergone several reforms (some of which have remained in the project stage) and innovations to its educational system; not only for its extension, but also for improving the teaching content in order to adapt it to the social realities and urgent needs of the country. The process of adapting the educational content to the historical, geographical, and cultural realities of the country, began in the early 1960s. The first attempts were deemed inappropriate. For a predominantly rural and agricultural country, 1967 reform aimed at "ruralizing" the school by sending significant number of rural youths under the age of 20 to school, with an important emphasis on manual and agricultural work. It was intended, on the one hand, to allow the school enrolment rate to triple by the recruitment of young people aged 12 to 15, and on the other hand to increase agricultural productivity by bringing new cultural knowledge and techniques to the students. During a three-year cycle, the school was supposed to train educated farmers in the *Centres d'Education Ruraux (CER)*, (it can be translated as Rural Education Centers. The evaluation of the rural school carried out in 1970 found the reform did not reach the expected objective as it increased discrimination and rural exodus of young people. It was then abandoned (Savadogo 2013).

After the failed attempt and the short-lived reforms in the 1960s, Burkina Faso undertook noticeable education reforms under Thomas Sankara (the leader of the Burkinabe Revolution) during the revolution. Reproaching the colonial school for "its content of enslavement and exploitation of man by man designed to exalt the superiority of French culture and to train local subordinate cadres in order to facilitate and perpetuate the colonial order", also rejecting the "a neo-colonial school that has essentially kept the defects of the colonial school of which it is the heir," the "revolutionary school" proposed in 1984 a new school that would lead to the transformation of the school into an instrument in the service of the Revolution. Thus, "the graduates who come out of it will have to be not in the service of their own interests and the exploitative classes, but at the service of the popular masses. But the reform could not see the light of the criticisms that have emerged in the General Assemblies and

The People's Commissions in charge of the ministerial sectors (CPM) and organized for this purpose. These include, above all, the very high cost of the reform and the disregard for diplomas, which ignores the international environment.” (Pilon 2003).

Further reforms took place in the early 1990s prioritizing basic education and stipulates, through the 1996 the Education Guidance Act, Article 17, which made education compulsory for children aged 6-16. This obligation remained conditional on the capacity of the educational facilities. This policy was to be gradually implemented from elementary to post-primary (lower secondary) education plans. The 10-year Plan for the Development of Basic Education (PDDEB) was decreed in 1999 but it was not effective until 2001. It helped achieve a gross enrolment rate of 70% in 2011.

The new education act of 1996 resulted in overcrowded classes that “*double flux*” (double shifts) and *multigrade* (double session) classes arose. Both started in 1992-1993 school year. Double shift classes were developed to address the problem of large numbers of students by improving the rate of supervision of pupils. This is a practice that is found mainly in large urban centers where students in the same class are divided into two groups that alternate courses, one group in the morning, and the other in the afternoon with a single teacher. The double session classes were designed to address the problem of underutilization of infrastructure and teachers in districts with very low levels of schooling. Thus, the same class includes students from different years of study (usually two); this allows for annual recruitment in three-classroom schools. Alongside double shift and double sessions classes, another type of school called *satellite school* was created.

Satellite schools, which began experimenting in the 1996-97 school year with 30 satellite schools, aim to improve school coverage in rural areas where many children cannot attend school due to the geographical distance from the nearest primary school. They welcome children aged 7 to 9 who are not yet in school living in villages more than 3 km from a classical primary school. The specificity of these schools, which consist only of the first three grades of elementary schools (CPI, CP2 and CEI), is that instruction is mostly provided in the local language. Students are expected to join the third-grade class at the nearest classical school. The Non-Formal Basic Education Centers (CEBNF) aim to support literacy policy by recruiting rural youth aged 10 to 15 every two years. They were set up at the same time as the satellite schools and provide four years of vocational training. A new formula for non-formal early childhood pre-schooling is being tested. It is called “*Bissongo*”. This experience of early childhood development through the combined care of communities and staff of the Ministry of Social Action and Family consists of implementing complementary feeding, health and nutrition education, parental support and education, community well-being, communication,

and child-to-child programs. The 10-year Basic Education Development Plan (PDDEB 2001-2010) has doubled the numbers for quantitative indicators of primary education over the period and a new Education Guide Act was decreed in 2007. Learning from the history of "failed" reforms of the education system, after successively that of rural education (1961), that of the Government of National Renewal (1979-84), as well as the aborted reforms of Mr. Crespin (1967) and the Revolution (1986), the 2007 reform was a response to the imbalances created by forty years of policies focused on primary education. Along with the PDDEB, it improved the schooling rates, number of teachers, and school infrastructures (MOE Burkina Faso, 2018).

Despite significance improvement, the goal of universal schooling for all in 2015 could not be reached in 2015 and a new 10-year Plan of the Basic Education Strategic Development Program (PDSEB 2012-2021) inclusive quality education for all is planned for 2021. According to this Plan, education for all the children of Burkina Faso can be attained through basic education continuum which aimed at grouping preschool, primary and lower secondary (renamed post-primary for this purpose) in a single cycle, i.e. in a continuum of compulsory basic education, so as to: better build the learning gains through curricula and programs centered on basic needs.

This reform brought about some confusion. First because secondary education and primary education belonged to different ministries (Ministry of basic education & Ministry of secondary and higher education). Second, the basic education curriculum was still to be developed to align with the skills desired for the education continuum. Moreover, the teacher training and management question i.e. initial and continuing education, management modalities, etc. were still to be adapted to the needs of basic education continuum. It also raises the relevance of the continuation of Primary School Leaving Certificate and the entrance examination to the post-primary and the infrastructural capacities (infrastructures) of lower secondary schools to accept all the students who completed primary school education. This reform requires thoughtful measures for a successful implementation. Some actions have already been taken in this regard, such as the development of a curriculum guidance framework for basic education that is awaiting re-identification, construction of new middle schools across the country, and the transfer of preschool and secondary education to the Ministry of National Education and Literacy (MENAPLN). As part of the implementation of the education policy, MENAPLN has introduced and carried out several actions to improve access and quality of formal and non-formal education and the management of the sector. These broad guidelines include the reintroduction of scholarships, the effectiveness of free lower secondary education, the implementation of educational infrastructure, the generalization of curricular reform, school canteens from preschool to upper

secondary, the strategic plan to build capacity for education staff, etc. (Website of the MOE, 2021). Due to social unrests during this 10-year period and now the covid-19 pandemic.

III.2. Educational policies and national curriculum of Japan

Throughout its history, Japan has focused on education. Even before the Meiji period (1868-1912), under the monarchy (Edo period) between 1603-1868, Japan had many *terakoya* schools, open to the children of ordinary people and samurai (heroes). The restoration of Meiji has undergone a complete overhaul of the education system. In the modern process during the Meiji period, according to Kuroda (2003), Japan has established an education system with the aim to:

1. Develop human resource.
2. Achieve social cohesion (develop a sense of belonging)
3. Introduce the meritocracy program (goal of success instead of birth (Oba, 2005)).

In 1872, the government decided to establish a new education system (*Gakusei*) for schooling and other purposes and saw it as an important factor in the acquisition of Western lands and the establishment of national unity. Primary education, compulsory for all children, increased dramatically during the Meiji period and became almost universal during the Taisho period (1912-1926). While primary education was compulsory and common to all, secondary education was optional and included a variety of methods, offered in one or two cycles by different types of institutions.

Japan has invited many foreign experts as experts or advisers. Strengthen its developing education system. At the same time, talented young Japanese were sent to European and American lands to study the culture and knowledge of those lands. Returning to Japan, they replaced these foreign experts, who were too expensive for the government. Indeed, the number of foreign experts dropped from 527 in 1875, the year of recording, to 77 in 1896. It is important to point out that there was no brain dislocation (Kuroda, 2003).

Saito, Y. (2009) states that the pre-war education system and the one used during World War II were characterized by a diversity of tracks. Depending on the theory and method of education, the 1910s and 1920s saw the introduction of the ideas of John Dewey and other educators and influence. An organization known as the New Education Movement was also heard in Japan. However, the trend of the ultranationalist gradually began to be more evident in Japanese education policies in the 1930's. In 1937, when the Sino-Japanese War broke out, war became increasingly important, and after Japan's entry into World War II, military education was strengthened, as well as the control of educational

ideas and content. In the final stages of the war, students are gathered to help with food and military supplies. After its defeat in World War II in 1945, Japan was controlled by the General Headquarters of the Allied Forces (GHQ) until 1951.

After World War II, the education system was fully operational under foreign occupation. Under the recommendation from the United States, the leader of the Allied Forces, a 6-3-3-4 system, is a tightly reinforced system compared to the old system. Under this program, the reduction of war power, democracy, and reconstruction, and the country moved forward. In 1946, a new constitution was proclaimed, proclaiming peace and democracy. In addition, the mission continued with a major post-war transformation of the Japanese education system. These changes have replaced the Japanese Imperial Rescript on Education. The changes included the School Education Act (1947), the Education Law Board (1948), the Social Education Act (1949), and the Independent Schools Act (1949). The new education system was designed with the following:

- (1) the transition from the pre-war System to a double system to a single track known as the 6-3-3-4 system;
- (2) the extension of compulsory education to nine years of study, including primary and secondary education;
- (3) admission, in terms of mixed education for boys and girls;
- (4) the establishment of districts, municipal Education Boards;
- (5) the abolition of ordinary schools and the establishment of a university teacher training program,

Defeated in the war with the poor, implementing these reforms was not an easy task, but they decided to move forward with their full implementation.

The post-war reforms were followed by the Industrial Promotion Act” in 1951, the “Science Education Promotion Act” in 1953, and laboratories and universities could apply for national funding to achieve the goals set by these laws. The next major revision took place in 1958 by the National Courses of Study (NCS) ‘period of moral education’ aimed at boosting nationalism. The main purpose of promoting anti-communism is to prevent Japan from escalating the Korean War and to protect Japan's "armed values and morals" following the conclusion of the Security Partnership Agreement between the United States and Japan. Another specific purpose of this new policy was to improve students' basic skills and to emphasize science and technology education. This transformation has yielded significant results as the central Japanese industry shifted from agriculture to the light industry, becoming a complex and chemical industry (cf. Ministry of Health, Labor and Welfare, 2013).

After a breakthrough in the mid-1950's and early 1970's, the oil crisis came, and the Japanese education authorities changed their outlook on education policies and goals in 1977. The NCS revision in 1977 emphasized humanity. It aims to make standards more flexible by increasing the scope of selected subjects and giving freedom to create and incorporate 'free classes' (Saito, Y., 2009). During this period, the middle industry shifted from the heavy and chemical industries to the service industries and brought about a cultural change where the price was placed on 'small and light' items rather than 'large and heavy' (Yoshimi, 2008).

However, in 1984, the Interim Council for Education Transformation, which dealt with education issues, was convened to respond to the Prime Minister's consultation. Four reports of the Council for Educational Reform (1985, 1986, 1987, and 1987) highlighted a nationalist approach that emphasizes awareness of Japanese people and traditional Japanese culture. Individual education and the introduction of lifelong learning were ensured as global trade, computer use and human aging progressed. Social studies and science courses were completed in the first and second grades of elementary school, and environmental life courses were recently introduced. Natural life lessons are lessons that have a strong children's tone in the sense that they focus on making children learn about specific activities and experiences in their lives. Moral education to cultivate patriotism was also emphasized (Nishioka K., 2017).

The collapse of the Soviet Union was felt in Japan as it shook the conflict between right and left Japan. From the late 1990s onward, the state of academic affairs changed dramatically. A review of the NCS in 1998 called for 'creation of schools with characteristics', meaning that 'each school aims to promote the interest of children in life and to make a difference in education'. Policies emphasizing school intelligence have been in place since 1998. A review of the NCS in 1998 introduced the PFIS, which did not have a textbook, which opened the way for curriculum development and led to a significant impact on schools. However, in 1999, critics began to argue that relaxed education policies brought about a decline in academic skills. After a while, the liberal education policy was forced to make a change, with a partial review conducted in the NCS in 2003 aimed at developing 'strong academic skills. The 2008 NCS Review is considered to be a learning force that includes the following three elements: (1) the acquisition of basic knowledge / skills, (2) the thinking, judgment and self-expression skills required to solve problems using your knowledge / skills and (3) a participatory learning environment (Nishioka. K., 2017). MEXT regularly reviews policies almost every decade within which small revisions are made until the next major revision.

An overview of Japanese education history shows why the Japanese education system is one of the best in the world. It remains one of the OECD's best performers in a program conducted by the

Program for International Student Assessment (PISA), a major international study of 15-year-old skills in terms of achievement quality, equitable access to education and value for money.

Although elementary and middle school education is part of compulsory education, the percentage of students who graduate from high school has reached 98%. High schools (a system that includes middle and high school) were established as a result of the 1998 Enforcement Regulations for the School Education Act, but they remain few. According to the School Basic Survey conducted by the Department of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology (MEXT) in the 2014 financial year, there were 20,852 primary schools, 10,557 middle schools, 4,963 high schools and 51 high schools in Japan (MEXT, 2014).

III.3. Educational policies and classroom instruction in Burkina Faso

The educational policies, reforms have ameliorated the gross schooling rate. The PDDEB, PDSEB, and Basic Education Continuum. However, these reforms exacerbated the issues for conducting lessons in overcrowded classes, classroom management, and the ever-changing pedagogical approaches.

With the improvement in the enrolment rate, a major phenomenon has emerged, that of overcrowded classes. Despite efforts in terms of infrastructure and human resources, large classes could not be avoided. According to official texts, Education of August 1994, the maximum number of students per class should be 65 in primary school, 70 for the first cycle of secondary education and 60 pupils for the second cycle. Despite these provisions, school's compliance with these standards has proved difficult due to the high demand for education of the population and the lack of resources (infrastructure, teaching staff). One of the consequences of this overcrowding in the classroom is obviously the slowing down or even hindering the proper functioning of educational activities. The concern for both researchers and education practitioners is to find a pedagogical solution to this problem, as the contemporary teacher Celestin Freinet put it, "Any overload of classes is always a pedagogical error" as quoted by (Pare-Kabore A, 2014:P). Considering statistics, it is possible to get an idea of the impact of high enrolment by comparing the average class sizes of each of the country's 13 regions with its average percentage of national exam success and with its promotion or repetition rates. In light of the statistics, it can be said that there are classes in both elementary and secondary education where the number of students exceeds the expected standard are not faring very well. However, the situation is worse in lower secondary. Today, it is common to see classes of 80, 90, 100 or even more than 100 students in several classes in lower-secondary Burkina Faso (Gamene, 2010). However, in general, the problem is less pronounced in secondary school than in primary school

because the PDDEB and PDSEB concentrated their efforts on Primary education from 2001 to 2014 when the implementation of the Basic education continuum to include lower secondary. Overcrowded classes pose challenges to classroom management pedagogical issues.

Large classrooms required different approaches and teaching methods than those applied in so-called normal classes, i.e., small classes. Normal classes are have less than 50 students; and that beyond 120 students, the class is not a large group but rather a "crowd" (Conombo et al as quoted by Kabore-Pare & Gambre-Idany , 2014). Large classes prompt teachers to use dogmatic methods or repetition and memorization. However, these are practices that do not arouse creativity and stifle any initiative from learners. Clearly, these so-called traditional methods do not allow students to think or be creative, rather they make them simple performers/robots. As school administration continues to assign each teacher a high number of students per class to meet demand for education, it creates major obstacles to the teaching / learning process. Teachers who are not trained to face such educational situations are often helpless and take refuge behind threats to hide or make up for their incapacity, their helplessness. The quality of education is thus shattered. To deal with this eventuality, the solution is to build more classes and recruit more teachers. This solution, however appropriate, risks remaining at the virtual stage because of the very fragile economy of Burkina Faso. So, there is the need to look for other ways to deal with the problem of large groups (Bayoulou, 2009).

Educational advisors and supervisors agree that when the size of a class exceeds a certain number, it is detrimental to teaching/learning process as the interaction becomes difficult. Everyone also agrees that large numbers pose an educational problem that must be resolved. Teachers unanimously believe that large groups constitute an obstacle to the implementation of certain teaching activities. This includes organizing group work, as the class then becomes more difficult for the teacher to control due to the noise the students make (Gassambe, 2011). Gambré-Idany (2012) observed that, for English teachers, large class sizes are an obstacle to the use of teaching methods as required for Communicative Language Teaching (CLT). They consider that it is a method which is not adapted to lower grades (1st grader in lower-secondary) of which we also know that the numbers are generally the highest. it would be an equally pernicious illusion to imagine that teachers are spontaneously adept at managing large groups. They must therefore be helped to do so through appropriate training as the reduction of class size cannot be reached soon.

The downsizing large classes in the Burkinabe context, as in many African countries with limited resources, is based on the development of teaching methods able to lighten the groups and make them more functional. These methods are, among others, the teaching of large groups and the related techniques as well as Computer-Assisted Instruction/Learning (CAI/CAL).

In addition, the application of large group pedagogy cannot be done by ignoring the curriculum or teaching programs at both the primary and secondary levels. According to the analysis of various education specialists, the integration of the pedagogy of large groups must be accompanied by a streamlining of school programs as well as their writing in terms of skills to be acquired by students.

The new programs must give students more autonomy by orienting them towards problem-solving, project-based learning, and personal research. In addition, programs must be developed in terms of skills to be acquired by students. In other words, our education system would benefit from promoting **Competence-Based Pedagogy**, commonly referred to as the **Competence-Based Approach** as well as **Project-Based Learning**. Such an approach in the design of the programs necessarily implies a new policy regarding teaching materials. However, the educational authorities need to have a clear plan on where they want to take the school to and how they do it.

The literature review shows that Burkina Faso educational policies look uncoordinated as there is no clear planned curriculum and approaches that streamlines with classroom practices and teaching materials, and in-service teacher training is not a priority. Not prioritized in-service training amidst permanent uncoordinated policies which most often follow offers from partners hinders the quality of the education, thus the scholastic abilities of the students. A new policy framework enacted in 2015 lead to the writing and experimentation at the 1st and 2nd grade of in element and lower-secondary level give hope to the end of the uncoordinated policies that marked the educational reforms since the independence. However, education supervisors do not only complain about not the lack of clear mechanisms for monitoring the application of the new approaches (Integrative Pedagogical Approach (API) and Social Constructivist Approach) in the classroom but also the lack of coherence with textbooks, initial and professional training, and assessment. Along the pedagogical reforms, decentralization of basic education is ongoing. There is an urgent need to speed up the process and equip the local authorities with the basic needs to help the schools to cope with the lack of infrastructure and teaching materials. Burkina Faso may learn how from the rich experience of educational reforms in Japan and how they are implemented in schools and translated into the Japanese society.

III.4. Educational policies and classroom instruction in Burkina Faso

The management of public primary schools is left to municipal education boards as founders. However, MEXT and educational boards exercise authority primarily in education management (staff management) and curriculum management (leadership administration). Education workers are

classified as municipal officials. However, municipal education boards have limited rights; they submit reports on teacher service and teachers' supervision to Prefectural Education Boards.

In Japan, the Constitution and the Constitution of Education provide for educational purposes, and on the basis of that, Education Boards and schools determine educational objectives. The educational objectives of the school reflect the educational philosophy of each school and various educational activities are carried out in schools to achieve the objectives. In Japan, typical local school curriculum is offered by Prefectural and Municipal Education Boards. They provide the local curriculum based on "The National Course of Study," which is the national curriculum.

In addition to the educational objectives, each school conducts its "annual administrative plan" as a standard plan at the beginning of the year. This guideline provides guidance for (1) grade, subject and fields, (2) Semester orientation programs, (3) monthly administrative programs, (4) Weekly and unit guidance programs, (5) Daily administrative programs and (6) Current course management programs. Plans are usually made from (1) to (6) and they are evaluated through classes and assessed periodically. The school also conducted its "Course of Study" earlier in the school year. This strategy is tailored to each subject and extracurricular activities such as moral education, specialized activities, and integrated study at each grade level.

Today in Japan, setting tangible educational goals and conducting specific assessments of the level achieved goals have been prioritized to determine individual progress. This method reflects previous information regarding the use of evaluation and assessment.

Curriculum development is a process that continuously assesses the school curriculum in view of social change, etc., and then develops it. It includes curricula at various levels, for example, schools, communities, and the national curriculum. In Japan, the implementation of the foundations of the Course of study and full involvement of each school in curriculum development began after the CERI (Center for Educational Research and Innovation) of OECD developed a concept called SBCD (School-based Curriculum Development). Curriculum development in Japan requires a set of procedures that must (1) set educational goals, (2) select learning activities, (3) select content, (4) plan learning experiences and content, (5) conduct evaluations, and (6) improve. Each school builds its own curriculum with this set of practical procedures.

Japan emphasizes the importance of building a creative and effective curriculum in each school. Research on the development of new and genuine curricula is underway at national and local levels.

After setting study and administrative objectives of the school and individual classes, teaching content is organized into units according to the actual conditions of student achievement based on the objectives of each grade and subject with the following requirements:

1. Define the objectives of each lesson and select appropriate teaching content to achieve the objectives of the units.
2. Organize units to fit the students, considering teaching quality, program content, and coherence.
3. Organize school events according to the local circumstances and seasons.

"Teaching materials" are very important for an effective classroom instruction. They model content that should be taught and ease its delivery. Textbooks are the main teaching materials, and some include documents, reference materials, and other object that the teacher chooses according to specific needs of students to achieve the goals of classroom activities. The time the teacher uses to select, interpret, and organize "teaching materials" according to classroom objectives is called "research on teaching materials." Japanese teachers spend a lot of time doing it.

Evaluation and assessment are conducted to help improve individual students and the whole class to help reach the class and school objectives and inform curriculum development. For instance, each class has a homeroom teacher who carefully report the assessment of each student's progress and ability to inform them of their performance, to set goals and to inform parents about their children's academic progress. Furthermore, class evaluations are meant to improve classes. while rating scores vary according to category objectives, key factors to consider are (1) the appropriateness of the content of the section according to students' development, (2) whether the content address and accommodate individual difference, (3) whether students are able to work effectively and are content with it) whether students have the opportunity to express their ideas about things they do not understand and (5) whether the materials and materials are used correctly. Finally, the evaluations of each individual student and class allow the evaluation of the curriculum, an important step in curriculum development. A comprehensive the curriculum is conducted to check whether the curriculum is designed and used effectively and to develop lessons. It is a multilevel including schools, communities, and government. The 'curriculum assessment' at school level is carried out in terms of (1) student achievement (2) school curriculum development plans, (3) community-curriculum relationships, (4) curriculum assessment results of the whole school and (5) school characteristics.

The "Integrated Study Period" was established under a revised NCS of 1998. This is a time when children can learn beyond the general curriculum by following the specific ideas identified in each school: primary and secondary schools. The objectives for this period is to develop and improve

problem-solving skills and qualifications by identifying issues, learning, applying critical thinking, interpreting, and working independently through crossover and integrated research and exploratory research, and learning how to learn and think, and how to independently solve problems and perform investigative tasks; and finally, you can do the self-examination. Students grow on their own through their skills, personality, and self-confidence in the classroom. At the same time, they develop the skills of a community group by collaborating or talking to classmates about different personalities and abilities. In classroom management, teachers provide leadership for each student and the whole class as a group.

In addition to integrated study, Japanese schools use a unique classroom and learning management. It is done from an educational perspective. The management system needs to be developed with a view to academic activities that include guidance on both subjects and extracurricular activities. Homeroom teachers need to first understand the characteristics and conditions of each student, identify the required group activities, and then set goals for class management for the year. The key objectives of the classroom are to develop student groups that work to enhance individual growth and have a positive impact on the education of each learner. Students themselves help determine the purpose of their classes. Objectives can be motto or slogans for each student in the class. Creating and pursuing such goals plays an important role in creating orderly classroom environments in which groups work and learning is individualized and contextualized. It is the teachers' responsibility to understand the growth and development of learners as individuals and groups and provide appropriate guidance to their students by keeping classroom objectives in mind. The objectives of the classroom reflecting the motto of the class are displayed primarily in the form of posters in the most visible areas of the classroom as reminders to both teachers and students.

Another subpoint of classroom management are classroom activities that serve as a single unit and include special activities that form part of the formal curriculum. These activities enrich and strengthen the daily life of the classroom and school" and "harmonize daily life with learning and improving health and safety. Partnership and mentoring activities are done by aligning classroom settings in a way that helps students address ethics by solving school and classroom health problems. They are safe and promote good mental health.

The objectives and content of the classroom activities have an impact on both group and group activities and day activities. Classroom activities involve a variety of classroom activities by performing individual assignments. Group-based activities include student collaboration in small groups by engaging in a variety of activities and activities. A day's work is a day-to-day task assigned to the whole class. Classroom management activities are integrated into the formal curriculum to

encourage learners to perform tasks voluntarily and independently. They are just as important as learning each lesson because they form the basis for establishing class groups. Students in charge of class activities have their names written on the wall in the classroom and the type of tasks they have to do. By showing that all learners share a variety of classroom activities, the responsibility and desire of students to participate actively in class activities increases.

Finally, there is a daily journal also referred to as a newsletter, which is published by some teachers as a one-way communication between teachers in the classroom in collaboration with students and parents. The content and methods used to publish newsletters vary between teachers. A newsletter can be an important way to get the class together. Newsletters have many functions. The most common task is to inform parents about the children's school life and planned school events. They have another important role of conveying to students the thoughts and ideas of the teacher and providing teacher guidance to students and their parents through classroom textbooks which are given to students and their parents. Through newsletters parents understand the situation of students in the classroom and are informed of the education policies and how homeroom teachers treat view students. Home teachers who have the ability to evaluate the results of their textbooks try to do the following: properly identify the students' circumstances as a group and inform them of relevant issues; asking parents about their level of understanding of teacher policies; encouraging parents to work with their children. Through textbooks, teachers also send messages to improve students' motivations for life and learning.

CHAPTER IV. IMPLICATIONS FROM THE COMPARATIVE STUDY FOR BURKINA FASO

One of the best ways to improve something is to emulate the good qualities of categories of others and change their ways of doing things. Burkina Faso is facing a crisis in its education system and must accept some good qualities of other countries like Japan and adapt them accordingly. It is important that Burkina Faso reaches effective compulsory free basic education for all the children. Japan is almost 100% literate thanks to the careful planning of the national curriculum, the guidance for the prefectural and municipal boards of education across the country on the implementation, adaptation, and integration of the curriculum accordingly. What lessons for educational policies, teacher trainers and classroom instruction in Burkina Faso?

IV.1. Implication for educational policies

Furthermore, in the face of the obvious failures of successive educational reforms, and the ongoing tottering reforms, the question is not whether we should develop the same models used since independence but develop a different, integrated, and selective model according to current needs and future goals. Indeed, many students are still being excluded from the formal system right now, due to inadequate policies, uncoordinated reform and a system inspired from the colonial system or inadequately copied and applied abroad. The desire for social development that the school has to offer in the eyes of the Burkinabe reaffirms the choice of one school that is right for all. A school that makes learning functional members of the society. Reforms which will just rely on the current framework combine with the lack of clear prescribed curriculum providing for teaching content and classroom instruction that will address ongoing challenges, meet short-, mid-, and long-term goals are likely to fail. Burkina Faso can take lesson curriculum development as done in Japan and how the different levels adapt, integrate, and impart it to the learners.

The Japanese education system is often described as the middle ground. MEXT, the lead authority for the development and implementation of national education policy, distributes public or educational resources at national, regional, and municipal levels, and directs national standards for curriculum, textbook development, and teacher training. Each of the 47 prefectures has its own education board responsible for coordinating education on its territory. Many lessons learned from Japan's educational experience are helpful for analytical purposes, but the risk hides a very important aspect of the Japanese education system. The program is designed not only to develop students' cognitive abilities, but also to instill social values in morals, fitness development and social cohesion for those students.

The Japanese public's response to the recent natural disaster, not only in the affected areas but throughout the country, provides a powerful indication of this (OECD, 2012).

Figure 1: Educational objectives and curriculum implementation chart in Japan

Source: Center for Research on International Cooperation on Educational Development, 2021
<http://www.criced.tsukuba.ac.jp/>

Everywhere in schools, there is evidence of efforts to reward hard work and perseverance, to commend students who take the challenge, to encourage students to use their school with other students and to take responsibility for helping others, rewarding modesty, and giving others credit for their good work. It is not hard to imagine how this kind of moral attention could affect many aspects of public health, from business ethics to health care, a sustainable environment to crime, and it is worthwhile to look at the possibility of a world ignoring this aspect of their children's education. In many ways, students are taught to respect their elders and teachers, to do right, to be orderly and orderly.

IV.2. Implication for curriculum design

In the 1980s, within the framework of resource development as a strategic component in the Burkinabe citizen acquisition of a new type by a new school marks the end of the previous educational reforms

of 1979 and the beginning of a new transformation project. The Revolutionary Regime therefore sets out the availability of an education system, which is almost identical to the previous one without the ideological (Marxist) side it has made clear, in line with the new planning proposal. Switching from basic level to polytechnic level will be automatic; that of polytechnic at the professional level, and at each level of innovation and research under the production phase, for a period of about two years (according to official announcements) and the requirements of the development plan. No student was to be excluded from the basic cycle and the polytechnic cycle. The cost of the project was estimated at 78 billion CFA Franc. Unfortunately, this change will never be implemented, as it is accused of being too expensive and wanting to keep young people in a position to meet the proposal to complete the diploma. Finally, it is the reforms that focus on primary education, proposed by the World Bank that was implemented (Savado, 2013). The PDDEB, PDSEB, and SCADD, set modest goals in line with the achievement of the MDGs and EFA objectives by the 2015 deadline. Even though schooling rate soared, the quality remains the same and the PNDES vowed to accelerate the year 2021, when we judge by the objectives and the amount of funding required. A lot of lower-secondary schools were built between 2015-2020 but the uncoordinated nature of the reforms and the rapid demographic growth make this progress look insignificant.

Ongoing curriculum revision may not yield the expected results if it is done with all the required expertise. It should include educational researchers, anthropologists, sociologists, researchers in didactics in each study discipline with clear objectives to reach at the end of each cycle i.e. elementary education, lower-secondary, and upper secondary. The curriculum and instruction should align with the nation goals and values with easy-to-teach/learn. Political focus on quantity may hamper the quest for quality curriculum and make it difficult to reach quality and inclusive education for all as stated in the 4th goal for Sustainable Development (SDG4).

Burkina Faso can learn from Japan, a country with clear and prominent educational standards across the board that provides a strong and consistent delivery chain where academic objectives translate into teaching programs and practices, as well as student learning. The national curriculum, which is reviewed every ten years is one of the major strengths of the Japanese education system. Theoretically, the curriculum is set by the Japanese Ministry of Education, Culture, Sport, Science and Technology (MEXT) with advice from the Supreme Council of Education. The curriculum is cohesive, with a strong focus on key themes and in-depth conceptualization, careful sequencing, and set at a very high level of cognitive challenge, even if it follows a more formal subject-based culture rather than a standard approach. In practice, key statistics involved in curriculum setting are university professors and service staff and Burkina Faso should rethink its system for teacher training.

Figure 2: Curriculum development model in Japan

Source: Center for Research on International Cooperation on Educational Development, 2021
<http://www.criced.tsukuba.ac.jp/>

IV.3 Implications for teacher-trainers

The uncoordinated educational policies caused overcrowded classes affecting classroom management and instruction. Some sporadic trainings were organized to help. Despite this training, many teachers in the field still struggle to support large groups. Some of them demand during the more training to start using the methods and an evaluation (Conombo et al., as quoted by Pare-Kabore, 2014). In other words, the teachers did not use the teaching methods of the large groups. The admission of volunteer teachers (i.e. without basic teacher training) to elementary school classrooms in the 1900s made matters worse. It should also be noted that the problem of teachers without professional qualifications is not limited to basic education, as secondary education is always known for employing teachers with Associate degrees, *licence* (Bachelor's) or *Maîtrise* (4-Year graduate level degree), or master's degree as the country faces a shortage of teachers for secondary schools. They are often recruited and sent directly to junior and high schools without pedagogical training. A lot of efforts have been done in this regard as elementary school teachers are recruited with the *Baccalaureat* (High school diploma) as opposed to the BEPC. In the same line, secondary school teachers will no longer be recruited with Associate degrees. They will be recruited with their bachelor's degree or Master and sent to the teacher-training college for one year of theoretical training and another year in a school setting where

they will be guided by experienced teachers and advised by educational advisors. To make this move more interesting, the teacher-training curriculum and the profile of the teacher trainers should be adapted along national curriculum. This will bring about a cohesive and coherent training system, teaching content, quality human resources to take the socio-economic development of the nation forward. Japan provides a good example of cohesion and coherence throughout the educational system.

The development of an effective teacher assessment system will be required to improve the performance of individual teachers and the effectiveness of the education system as a whole. Designing teacher assessment methods is not easy and requires improvement and accountability goals to be carefully measured. Combining performance improvement and accountability in a single teacher assessment process raises many challenges, and comparative research on the performance of different models is beginning to emerge.

But no matter how good pre-service education can be, it cannot be expected to prepare teachers for all the challenges they will face in all their careers. Data from the first OECD Teaching and Learning International Study (TALIS) study show that more effective development methods are often adopted by teachers themselves, in many countries, who are willing to even contribute to the cost of such education financially and temporarily. As mentioned earlier, Japan has a strong tradition in teacher development through collaboration between teachers and learning subjects in schools.

At the same time, international comparisons do not offer much support in the belief that reductions in class size indicate a more efficient use of additional resources. In fact, the results from PISA suggest that the best-performing countries prioritize quality teaching in class size. The problem is that a reduction in the size of the classroom in Japan has largely contributed to further public investment in education. This has left a limited space for some of the most important investments in building learning outcomes and attracting teacher careers, especially teacher salaries (which have fallen sharply, compared to other professional salaries since the 1990s (OECD, 2012).

Figure 3: School based-in-service training model in Japan

Source: Center for Research on International Cooperation on Educational Development, 2021
<http://www.criced.tsukuba.ac.jp/>

IV.4. Implication for Classroom practices

Burkina Faso has got overcrowded classrooms as a result of mass schooling from the PDDE policy. Pedagogy for large classes are being explored but that can only serve as a short-term solution as overcrowded classes do not allow teacher to use diverse teaching methods and strategies, not mentioning differentiated instruction for special need students or teaching multilevel classes. Exploring solution to teach large classes, Pare-Kabore (2014) says that the teacher can share his teaching responsibilities with high performing students. It consists of dividing the class into a few smaller groups, taking care to identify in each group a more comfortable student to give him or her a "group" responsibility. This student, after teaching the collaboration provided by the teacher, will take it upon himself to have his colleagues repeat what was seen in the large group with the teacher; Thus, he becomes a student coach the teacher can rely on to review what has been taught to the whole class. Such a practice not only promotes a spirit of solidarity among students but also promotes healthy competition between students. Because each student will want to make an effort to be his or her guardian. Note that this is an appropriate option for elementary school students and high school beginners. Integrated Searching for Ideas This is a collaborative process of thinking and combining

all students' ideas about a subject or problem given very quickly. This approach can be used regardless of group size and involves students in building knowledge by developing quick and automatic ideas. It stimulates thinking and thus helps students' ingenuity. However, it requires discovery and good motivation for them.

Furthermore, it is also possible to use academic debate which requires the division of students into small groups to resolve a problem. Each student thinks first about the matter, and then an exchange takes place in small groups; the researchers of each group identified the ideas they presented when compiling the work of the different groups. This strategy acquaints students with each effort and trains them to work in groups. It is also possible to use a variety of learning situations by drawing in different school subjects. Students organized into small groups will perform different but coherent tasks.

CAI/CAL can solve the problem of large groups. E-learning is developing and establishing itself as an important working tool in all areas of work, thanks to the proliferation of Information and Communication Technology (ICT). Indeed, thanks to a computer, teachers can prepare their lessons online. For students, it enables them to take ownership of online course content and enable them to accomplish other learning activities. ICT has thus transformed the world and education. It is a good game to equip primary, secondary, and tertiary institutions with computer and Internet. Indeed, ICTs make it easier to alleviate the shortage of educational materials. Student books can even be replaced with digital tablets as is the case today in some countries. However, this requires addressing natural ICT problems in Burkina Faso such as the lack of electricity, telephones, and rooms.

Instructional guidance is not very clear in Burkina Faso especially in secondary education to allow teachers, especially those hired without pre-service training apply successful teaching methods. In Burkina Faso, apart from the last grades in elementary, lower secondary, and upper-secondary, where students sit for national exam, teachers rarely cover all the items in the textbook and syllabus. Therefore, students accumulate gaps throughout the cycle that it is hard for them to understand some concepts at the last grade of a given cycle. Unlike Burkina Faso Moreover, Japanese teachers do not choose which parts of the book they will use; they are expected to teach all textbooks, which is a sure sign that all Japanese students of the same level are expected to study the same thing across the country.

Because of all of this, everyone - students, teachers, and parents - knows what it takes to get a degree, depending on the content studied and the level of performance required to earn it. Students cannot progress to the next level - either in the workplace or in further education - unless they show that they are ready to do so. The first is that in a qualifying society, high school and university admission tests

represent the gates of status in Japanese society. The Japanese strongly believe that success in these tests depends more on hard study than on internal intelligence.

At first glance, the Japanese method of teaching violates the principles of the most common concept. There is less teaching technology than in many other countries and few educational resources of some kind. Students are often not divided into skill groups; no special classes are gifted, and students are not forced to go to the next level or more if they appear to have special ability. Similarly, students are not held back when faced with difficulties. Unlike teachers in Western lands, most Japanese teachers accept relatively large classes because, they think, more students are likely to come up with more problem-solving strategies that other students can learn from. And the variety of ideas that many students have developed can be used to stimulate conversation. In science subjects, for example, there will be a wide range of results from a web-based assessment that can be used to test problem-solving strategies and promote a deeper understanding of the subject matter under study (OECD, 2012).

Of course, there is no doubt that past and present reductions in classroom size present an opportunity for Burkina Faso to promote new teaching methods and try new teaching methods, including greater emphasis on collaborative work, project-based learning and greater communication between students and teachers. When classes have reasonable sizes, Burkina Faso can try the newsletter system or organize periodic open school days to keep parents abreast of how their offspring are faring.

Figure 4: Class newsletters informing students' progress

Source: Center for Research on International Cooperation on Educational Development, 2021
<http://www.criced.tsukuba.ac.jp/>

CONCLUSION

The main purpose of this paper was to take lessons from Japan in an effort to inform the ongoing curriculum reforms of the Burkinabe education system so that it can improve the quality of the workforce. The rationale of this study is that educational reforms are not well-planned or ignore some essential aspects of curriculum and instruction. The problem was that the Education Acts such as 1996 and 2007 stayed at the policies stage and took years for the MOE of Burkina Faso to engage curriculum reforms which are still ongoing. It is important to notice that early educational policies during the restoration period and its strong commitment to education has boosted post-war economic growth rapidly, and because of its human quality, the country is one of the major contributors to domestic production. High technology with a high value added. Since the 1980s almost boast the most developed countries, economically and academically. The way Japan develops and implement its educational and curricular reforms show an ingenious planning to reach clear goals. It included the essential elements of curriculum development such as the (1) terms and content, learning and teaching methods, learning assessment, (2) room for adjustments (3) core objectives and skills to be developed (4) and now 21st century skills as global trade and the ICT shift is rapidly evolving.

Burkina Faso should involve communities, researchers, teachers, and students to get a curriculum that can help reach its noble objectives set in the 2007 Education Guidance Act. All Burkinabe teachers need to have pre-service and in-service training to their teaching techniques, methods and strategies as curriculum and instruction are dynamic. Learners like the use of digital and ICT in the classroom as it provides a relaxed classroom atmosphere, full of features and practical in rural or urban teaching environments (Malgoubri, 2019). However, CAI/CAL learning may not be implemented until teachers have the right training to do so and most schools equipped with ICT materials. Lack of adequate training is the main reason why you can see computers as decoration in schools that have them. However, they are modern teaching tools that require adequate training so that teachers can deliver information effectively.

In addition, a quick and adequate salary for teachers will go a long way in encouraging successful emulation in schools to attract more talented teachers. This will lead teachers to even pay for their own professional development. Coupled with a national curriculum and clear objectives, teachers can be fairly evaluated based on the attainment of the objective and students' and parents' satisfaction.

Furthermore, the government should continue its efforts to build secondary schools, and more teachers should be hired and trained to ensure a reasonable teacher-to-student ratio. Effective teaching is difficult in over-crowded classes.

Many nations are envious of Japan for its clear and ambitious standards across courses across the board, and the accompanying chains that are introduced when academic principles translate into high quality teaching programs and practices, as well as student learning. Many observers point out that what matters most in Japanese education is the quality of its teachers. But demands on Japanese teachers continue to rise. Teachers were asked to equip students with the skills they needed to become active citizens and workers in the 21st century. They are asked to customize the learning experience to ensure that every student can succeed and to cope with the growing diversity in their classrooms and the diversity of learning styles. They also need to keep up to date with innovation in education, teaching, and digital services (OECD, 2012).

Finally, since school-based results are a result of what happens in the classroom, only the most effective changes in the classroom can be expected to work. Teachers' involvement in the development and transformation of education is therefore important, and school reform will not work unless it is supported from the bottom up.

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